

**CURRENT ISSUES OF INCREASING THE COUNTRY'S
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ABSTRACT

This article discusses the possibilities of manufacturing products in Uzbekistan and exporting them abroad, issues of increasing investment attractiveness in exporting products abroad. Also, existing problems in the production of export-oriented products are analyzed.

In today's era of globalization, exports play an important role in the economic development of every country. After independence, the Republic of Uzbekistan also pays great attention to developing its economy, actively participating in international trade, and increasing its export potential. Export potential not only ensures the economic stability of the country, but also strengthens its position in the world market. Increasing export potential is certainly one of the tasks facing countries.

Export potential is understood as the ability, volume, and quality of a country to supply products and services to foreign markets. Uzbekistan currently aims to accelerate economic growth through the development of exports, and this is being effectively implemented in practice.

Export is of great importance for the country's economy, the reasons for which can be expressed as follows:

Firstly, it provides the country with foreign exchange earnings;

Secondly, it develops production;

Thirdly, it increases the possibility of organizing new production in the regions;

Fourthly, it creates new jobs;

Fifth, the country's position in the international arena will increase.

That is why the expansion and development of exports in Uzbekistan is one of the priority areas of state policy.

Increasing the quality of products and production volumes based on the effective use of modern technologies and innovations in the economy and their modernization is of urgent importance today. The basis of financial support for business entities is special loans, subsidies and grants aimed at exports.

It is also necessary to create a favorable investment climate for attracting foreign investment projects and developing enterprises.

To ensure timely and high-quality delivery of products, logistics services are provided, as a result of organizing and managing an effective supply chain, which ensures successful and fast high-quality delivery of products.

Ensuring the successful competition of enterprises in international markets requires the effective use of the above tools.

Organizational structures also play an important role in increasing the export potential of entrepreneurship. For example, agencies for promoting the sale of products abroad: special agencies have been established for exporting business entities. Agencies provide practical assistance to entrepreneurs in carrying out their activities of selling products abroad, provide advice, and provide them with the necessary information.

To date, the export potential of our country has significantly improved and is increasing. In particular, economic reforms, attracting investments, and comprehensive support for entrepreneurship have a significant impact on export growth. As of 2025, Uzbekistan's export volume exceeded \$ 30 billion. This indicator shows that it is growing year by year. The country's export geography has also expanded and now covers more than 100 countries. Positive changes are also observed in the structure of exports. Previously, it relied mainly on the export of raw materials, but now the share of finished products is increasing. Uzbekistan's exports consist of several main sectors:

Firstly, gold exports account for the largest share of the country's exports. Uzbekistan is one of the world's largest gold producers. Gold exports provide a significant amount of foreign exchange earnings to the state budget.

Secondly, exports of industrial products also play an important role. These include metals, chemical products, fuel and energy resources. In recent years, as a result of the modernization of industry, exports in this sector have been increasing.

Thirdly, exports of agricultural products are also developing rapidly. Uzbekistan exports fruits and vegetables, melons and other agricultural products to many countries. These products are distinguished by their ecological purity and quality.

Fourthly, exports of the textile industry are also important. Exports of finished cotton products, clothing and fabrics are increasing. The introduction of deep processing in this sector is increasing export potential.

In order to further increase exports in the country, we believe that it is appropriate to systematically address the following issues.

It is necessary to accelerate exports abroad, not in the form of raw materials, but in the form of finished products, which will be achieved by creating added value and organizing additional production, creating jobs;

Production activities require a convenient infrastructure, and these issues should be resolved gradually;

It is necessary to improve the road infrastructure for transporting raw materials, as well as pay attention to the development of the railway;

Improving the implementation of international standards in the organization of production and the preparation of financial statements is a priority.

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